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Ultra-Stable, spatially uniform monochromatic beam generation via active flux stabilization and fractional Talbot Self-Imaging

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ABSTRACT

Laser-based stable and uniform sources are necessary in various radiometry applications such as spectroradiometry, imaging, materials processing and various device characterizations. This study presents an optical system that produces a highly stable and homogeneous monochromatic beam using commercially available optical components. The stabilized laser flux fluctuates within ± 40 ppm over multiple hours of operation. Beam homogenization is achieved through a microlens array-based beam integrator, expanding the beam into a uniform square profile exceeding $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ with a spatial uniformity above 99.6 %. For a coherent source, the homogenized expanded beam is an array of regularly spaced, narrowly packed light spots (beamlets) of identical intensity. A computational model based on Fresnel diffraction, Fourier analysis, and fractional Talbot self-imaging phenomenon has been used here to predict the beam's irradiance distribution and behaviour. The model showed good agreement with experimental results. With an output irradiance expanded uncertainty falling as low as 0.46 %, the system provides a precise and reliable platform for optical measurements calibration and device characterization.

1. Introduction

The ability to deliver highly temporally stable, spatially uniform, and monochromatic light is of high importance in various industrial, medical and scientific areas, including calibration and characterization of various optical instruments, material processing and vision applications. This need is particularly expressed where highly precise and standardized experimental setups are required to ensure comparability, repeatability, and measurement accuracy.

In environmental sciences, accurate measurements of Solar Spectral Irradiance (SSI) are important for understanding the Sun's energy output across different wavelengths [1]. State-of-the-art instruments for measuring SSI are spectroradiometers, which are sophisticated devices that require regular laboratory characterization and calibration. These characterizations include determining spectral response functions (SRF) for broadband or narrowband spectroradiometers [2]. A temporally stable, spatially expanded and homogeneous, monochromatic beam, particularly when combined with highly reliable detection systems, offers a promising novel calibration method and SRF determination. Such systems already attracted attention to shorten the traceability to the SI (International System of Units) chain compared to conventional

calibration methods [3,4].

Characterization of certain photovoltaic (PV) cells, particularly multi-junction laser power converters, have been reported to require alternative approaches for precise irradiance measurements, as multi-junction devices exhibit significantly different behaviours under broadband versus monochromatic light [5,6]. Requirements are for monochromatic, flat-top beam profiles with varying sizes to accommodate various cell sizes and architectures. Temporal stability is equally critical for maintaining consistency over the measurement period. Spatial uniformity of the laser beam intensity has also been reported critical for accurate irradiance determination, as flat-top beams with high uniformities allow for flexible positioning of the test cell in the x-y plane and provide consistent irradiance measurements regardless of sample size or position. For PV applications, these requirements are defined by the IEC 60904-9 standard, where Class A solar simulators require temporal variations below 0.5 % for short-term instability and spatial non-uniformity of less than 2 % [7].

Temporally stable and spatially uniform beams have also found application and further need of development in various vision applications [8]. Applications such as widefield fluorescence microscopy use spatially non-uniform illumination sources such as lasers and LEDs,

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which lead to position-dependent excitation and emission of a sample labelled with fluorophores. This non-uniformity hinders the accuracy and reliability of quantitative analyses [9]. While various software-based corrective post-processing algorithms have been developed, hardware-based beam-shaping techniques are still necessary.

Modern commercial homogenizers based on beam integrators report output deviations of $\pm 2\%$ at beam scales from millimeter to centimeter, with transmission rates above 50%. Standard Kohler integrators with two microlens arrays are reported to produce uniform flat-tops from single-mode lasers with 2–10% intensity spatial variations [9–12]. Refractive beam shapers based on field-mapping techniques obtain similar uniformity deviations within 5% at transmission rates above 90% [13,14], however their output diameter and plane are usually fixed. Other beam shaping approaches such as spatial modulators can provide similar results, but at higher costs, complexity and lower transmission efficiencies.

Combinations of temporal and spatial stabilization of monochromatic intensities have been studied in several applications[15–18]. Integrating sphere-based systems have been used to achieve temporal stabilities as low as 900 ppm over half-hour operation and spatial uniformities below 0.5% in selected parts of the output beam [15,19,20]. However, such approaches are not well suited when large, free-space, flat-top beams with controlled directionality and low optical losses are required. Additionally, integrating spheres tend to fluoresce at certain wavelengths [20]. 3–4% spatial uniformity and ~ 0.3 –0.6% temporal stability were achieved, but temporal stability duration still a limiting factor [19]. Other irradiance-stabilization systems have reported $k = 2$ uncertainties around 1% [16,21], with temporal stabilities near 500 ppm and spatial non-uniformities below 1%.

In this study, we suggest a novel optical system producing a temporally ultra-stable, spatially highly uniform monochromatic light beam using standard, commercially available optical components that can be used in any laboratory. Temporal stabilization is achieved using a high-speed liquid crystal modulator paired with a beam flux monitoring photodiode, reducing temporal variability to as low as 40 ppm over 6-hour continuous operation, and remaining within 300 ppm for durations of at least 48 h of operation.

The optical system can produce either a homogeneous Gaussian beam, or a spatially uniform flat-top expanded square profile above $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ with homogeneity exceeding 99.6% (expressed as relative deviation to the mean), as characterized by scanning a $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ photodiode across the irradiance distribution. Additionally, we suggest a simple model based on Fresnel diffraction, Fourier Analysis and Talbot self-imaging to compute the diffracted field, predict dimensions and light intensity pattern of the beam at a selected propagation distance. The model was used to identify the conditions of spatial homogeneity, beam expansion and resolution, and showed good accordance with experimental results.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Equipment

Si photodiodes. High sensitivity photodiodes ($5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ S1337-66BQ from Hamamatsu, $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ SM05PD2B from Thorlabs) have been used to scan the expanded beam for homogeneity measurements.

Beam profiler. Beam images were captured using a WinCamD-LCM CMOS beam profiling camera (DataRay Inc.).

Laser sources. A diode pumped 475 nm blue laser from Crystal Laser (DL-473-010-S) was used in this study for the 475 nm monochromatic emission. The laser exhibits a spectral linewidth of $< 0.1 \text{ pm}$ and a peak wavelength at 475 nm. The laser beam operates in a single transverse (Gaussian, TEM₀₀) mode, with a beam quality factor $M^2 < 1.2$. The beam is diagonally linearly polarized with an extinction ratio 100:1. The output beam flux is approximately 10 mW.

A Helium-Neon (He-Ne) red 632.8 nm laser from Thorlabs was used

additionally in this study for measurements in the red range of the visible spectrum. The laser has a spectral linewidth of $< 4 \text{ pm}$ and emits an output beam in a single TEM₀₀ mode. He-Ne laser is randomly polarized, and its maximum beam flux reaches 5 mW.

LPC. A laser power controller (LPC) from Brockton Electro-Optics Corp. (BEOC) has been used for laser power control and temporal stabilization. Typically, the LPC system operates in the visible and NIR range (425 to 1700 nm), allowing vertically polarized input laser beam diameters up to 4 mm. The manufacturer guarantees a long-term temporal stability of $\pm 300 \text{ ppm}$. The LPC has been paired with a remote monitor photodetector (EXD-LPC, from BEOC) and a 10:90 (R:T) Non-Polarizing Beamsplitter (BS037, Thorlabs) to regulate the LPC independently with the sampled beam.

Half-wave plate. A half-wave plate is used to rotate the linear polarization angle from 45° to vertically polarized laser beam, required for the LPC.

Spatial Filter. A spatial filter system (KT311(/M), Thorlabs) has been used to circularize, spatially homogenize the output Gaussian laser beam. In the system, an aspheric $f = 9.6 \text{ mm}$ lens (C060TMD-A, Thorlabs) has been coupled with a $15 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ pinhole. Additionally, a $f = 13.86 \text{ mm}$ lens (C560TME-A, Thorlabs) has been placed after the pinhole for laser beam collimation post spatial filtering.

Microlens array. Two aperture-less $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ Fused Silica Micro Lens Arrays (MLA) (18-00244, Suss Microoptics, cylindrical lenses, pitch = $250 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, ROC = 0.75 mm , thickness = 2.25 mm) have been combined with a diverging lens for beam expansion and homogenization.

Optical Beam Shutter and Optical Beam Shutter Controller. An automatically controlled optical beam shutter controller (Thorlabs SH1 SC10) cycles through open/closed states to ensure dark current measurements.

XYZ motorized stage. Three individual motorized translational stages (8MT50-100BS1, Standa) have been combined into a XYZ motorized translational setup. With a detector mounted, this stage has been used to evaluate the spatial distribution of irradiance of the expanded and homogenized beam.

Electronics. Keithley 6517B electrometer has been used for detectors photocurrent measurements.

HM8143 (Rhode & Schwarz) three-channel arbitrary power supply has been used in this study for applying bias Voltage.

Software.

Simulations, data processing and analysis have been produced with Python.

MATLAB (MathWorks) software has been used, via serial communication interface (RS232), as a platform for control and communication between measurement devices, such as the electrometer, power supply, motorized stage, optical shutter, and a computer, real-time data acquisition, processing, graphical display of acquired data result.

2.2. The optical setup.

The aim of this setup is to combine aforementioned components (Section 2.1) to generate a temporally stable and spatially homogeneous laser beam. The optical setup developed in this study is presented in Fig. 1:

The output laser beam is directed with mirror M1 towards the half-wave plate (angled at 22.5°), which modifies the polarizing angle of the 475 nm laser from 45° to 90° (vertical) polarization, ensuring reception of the beam by the LPC. Inside the LPC, the Liquid Crystal modulates and stabilizes the laser beam flux. After exiting the LPC, the redirected by M2 laser beam travels through the spatial filter. At the output of the spatial filter, the beam is spatially uniformized to a clean, circular Gaussian shape. The beam is collimated by an additional converging lens placed after the spatial filter. The M3 mirror reflects the beam towards the beamsplitter, where a portion (10%) of the incident beam is sampled and refracted to the Remote Detector, which acts as a

Fig. 1. Schematics describing the optical setup.

feedback loop to the LPC for laser flux stabilization. This sampling and feedback part has been implemented at these later stages of beam propagation to ensure the fluctuations caused by both the Spatial Filter and the Laser Source are compensated by the LPC. The transmitted portion (90 %) of the temporally stabilized beam travels then through the Optical Beam Shutter, which blocks further beam propagation during dark measurements. During Signal Measurements, the Optical Shutter is open, letting the beam propagate either directly to the photodetector system if the desired beam is Gaussian, or through the Beam Homogenizer system for beam expansion and homogenization.

2.3. Beam homogenizer.

To achieve an expanded highly uniform beam profile, a custom beam homogenizer (Fig. 2) has been designed to expand and homogenize the temporally stabilized, Gaussian circular laser beam.

Loss-less beam-shaping for uniform beam generation is often obtained using integrators. In beam integrators technique, the input beam is split into multiple smaller beamlets, which are redistributed in an output plane with the desired irradiance profile [22,23]. Integrators typically consist of lens arrays and a Fourier lens and can be used with

highly coherent input beams if the speckle effects become less relevant.

In this setup, the custom beam homogenizer consists of two cylindrical microlens arrays and a diverging lens positioned before the MLAs. Each lenslet array splits and expands the input Gaussian laser beam into a one-dimensional linear irradiance distribution, effectively homogenizing the beam along one axis. By aligning two such cylindrical microlens arrays cross-positioned relatively from each other, with their lenslet axes oriented orthogonally, the input beam is split into beamlets distributed two-dimensionally, effectively shaping the beam into a square “flat-top” profile. Traditionally, a condenser (Fourier) lens is typically used to converge the beamlets in the output plane. In this study, however, such lens has been omitted to avoid non-uniformities caused by lens aberrations.

A diverging lens is placed before the arrays to expand the initial Gaussian laser beam to illuminate a sufficient number of microlenslets. The lens should be positioned to allow the laser beam to cover most of the lenslets without overfilling the MLA aperture, avoiding edge effects. In this setup, a diverging lens ($f = -75$ mm) is positioned 250 mm before the MLAs. The initial Gaussian collimated beam, after passing through the negative lens diverges and reaches the first microlens array (MLA1) where it is expanded to a $1/e$ diameter of 8 mm, slightly smaller than the

Fig. 2. Custom beam homogenizer is integrated in the optical setup. A diverging lens and a pair of MLA uniformly distribute the irradiance in a $55 \times 55 \text{ mm}^2$ square surface. In this setup, uniformities of $> 99\%$ are achieved in a plane situated between 350 mm and 370 mm distance from the beam homogenizer. A 99.6 % uniformity is achieved at 360 mm.

10 mm aperture of the MLA. MLA1 homogenizes the beam in one dimension (X), reshaping the circular Gaussian profile into a uniform, line-shaped profile along the X-axis. To homogenize the beam in the perpendicular dimension (Y) and modify the beam profile into a flat-top, square-shaped diverging beam, a second microlens array (MLA2) is placed immediately (at a distance under the effective focal length of the lenslets) after MLA1, oriented at a 90° rotation around the optical axis relative to MLA1. Thus, combination of both MLAs produces homogenisation and expansion in two dimensions.

2.4. Beam homogenizer modelling

A Fourier-analysis-based model can be applied to design a beam homogenizer prior to experimental validation. It allows the user to select components, define their relative positioning, and locate the observation plane matching the desired output beam properties.

In this study, the 2D intensity pattern in the near-field of the radiation emerging from the beam homogenizer (so-called Talbot carpet) is generated numerically using approximations to scalar diffraction theory. The Fresnel numbers $N_F = \frac{(L/2)^2}{\lambda z}$ in this setup configurations and selected components are typically high ($N_F > 100$), with observation plane distance z varying from 50 mm up to 450 mm, aperture limit L set at 10 mm, and a fixed wavelength λ at 475 nm. This clearly indicates an operation in the Near-Field regime and suitability of the Fresnel approximation to compute field propagations[24].

Our model results from applying the angular spectrum approach and Fast Fourier Transforms (FFT) of a rectangular periodic phase transforming structure (MLA) illuminated by an expanding Gaussian beam. The model is implemented using Python.

First, the system of two cross-positioned microlens arrays acts as the diffracting 2D structure positioned at $z = 0$ and represents aperture, grating and lensing effect of each microlens, and is modelled as the amplitude transmittance function:

$$t_{MLA}(x, y) = \left[\text{comb}\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) \text{comb}\left(\frac{y}{p}\right) * \left(\text{rect}\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) \text{rect}\left(\frac{y}{p}\right) e^{-j\frac{\pi}{2f}(x^2+y^2)} \right) \right] \bullet \text{rect}\left(\frac{x}{L_x}\right) \text{rect}\left(\frac{y}{L_y}\right) \quad (2.1)$$

Where,

- the Dirac comb $\text{comb}\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta\left(\frac{x}{p} - n\right)$ defines the periodic positions of lenslets (spaced by p , the pitch of the MLA)
- the first set of “rect” rectangle functions defining the aperture of each lenslet.
- the exponent term being phase transformation effect of a lenslet (of focal point f) on the incident wave of wavelength λ .
- The second set of rectangular functions defining the limits of the overall aperture (MLA) with L_x, L_y being the limits in x and y coordinates respectively.

Below (Table 1) are summarized the essential input parameters used for the model. Parameters related to the MLA originate from the 18–00244 Suss MLA specifications.

The periodic phase modulation of the Gaussian beam by the MLA generates multiple diffracted orders that interfere during propagation, producing the repeating self-images known as the Talbot effect. The transmitted field $U(x, y, 0)$ through the aperture (MLA) at $z = 0$ illuminated by the complex incident laser beam $U_{gaussian}$ is defined as:

$$U(x, y, 0) = t_{MLA}(x, y) \bullet U_{gaussian}(x, y) \quad (2.2)$$

With

Table 1

Summary of main input parameters integrated into the computation of the diffracted field.

Parameter	Abbreviation	Value
MLA pitch	p	250 μm
Focal length (lenslets)	f	1.56 mm
MLA side dimension	L_x, L_y	10 mm
Propagation distance of the diffracted field emerging from the MLA	z	50–450 mm (Step: 0.6 mm)
Gaussian beam diameter incident on the MLA	$2w(z_{mla})$	8 mm
Wavelength	λ	475 nm

$$U_{gaussian}(x, y) = \frac{w0}{w(z_{mla})} \exp\left[-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{w^2(z_{mla})}\right] \exp\left[jkz + jk\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2R(z_{mla})} - j\phi(z_{mla})\right] \quad (2.3)$$

Where $w(z_{mla})$ is the $1/e$ radius of the beam incident on the MLA (z_{mla}), $w0$ the waist, $z0$ the Rayleigh range, $R(z_{mla})$ radius of curvature of the wavefront and the Gouy phase:

$$\phi(z) = \tan^{-1} \frac{z_{mla}}{z0} \quad (2.4)$$

The objective is to calculate the resulting field $U(x, y, z)$ at an observation plane at a distance z from the aperture. This involves propagating the transmitted through MLA field $U(x, y, 0)$ using angular spectrum method of analysis, where $U(x, y, 0)$ is decomposed into simpler spatial Fourier components. Each component is propagated using the transfer

function $\exp\left[j2\pi \frac{z}{\lambda} \sqrt{1 - (\lambda f_x)^2 - (\lambda f_y)^2}\right]$ through free space to a position z . During propagation, each component of the angular spectrum acquires a phase delay. After propagation, the field amplitude at an observation plane z is then reassembled by summing up with inverse Fourier-Transform the contributions of complex-exponential functions of the angular spectrum, yielding $U(x, y, z)$. Thus, the field emerging from the MLA is computed using a transfer function and the angular spectrum of the field at the aperture plane:

$$U(x, y, z) = FT^{-1} \left\{ FT[U(x, y, 0)] \bullet \exp\left[j2\pi \frac{z}{\lambda} \sqrt{1 - (\lambda f_x)^2 - (\lambda f_y)^2}\right] \right\} \quad (2.5)$$

Where z is the position of the observation plane of the propagated field, f_x, f_y are the spatial frequencies,

FT and FT^{-1} are respectively Fourier Transform of the field at the aperture plane and inverse Fourier Transform of the propagated angular spectrum.

The intensity of the complex field at a propagation distance z is then reconstructed using:

$$I(x, y, z) = |U(x, y, z)|^2 \quad (2.6)$$

The 2D intensity pattern is built by computing intensity profiles $I(x, y, z)$ at incremental propagation distances z , with one lateral coordinate (y) fixed for 2D visualization of the intensity carpet.

It can be noted that in the near-field region, the 2D intensity distribution generated by illuminating a periodic structure with coherent light exhibits repeating self-images at regular intervals (Talbot lengths) along the beam's propagation direction as will be discussed later.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Irradiance spatial homogeneity

Near-field diffractions behind periodic structures illuminated by a

spatially coherent wave create interesting patterns leading to self-images of the periodic grating, contrast reversals and subimages at regular intervals along the propagation direction. This self-imaging phenomenon where the output light field shows a periodicity in propagation direction is called the Talbot effect [24–26], which also appears for the foci of microlens arrays. The divergence and expansion of the Gaussian beam prior to its incidence on the microlens arrays allow to uniformly cover most of the microlenses, allowing the self-imaging and fractional Talbot effect to take place.

Simulations of the intensity profile $I(x, 0, z)$ corresponding to the diffracted field emerging from the MLA-based beam homogenizer, which was illuminated by a diverging Gaussian beam, is pictured in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3(a) is a top-down view 2D transect at $y = 0$ of the simulated intensity pattern through intensity profiles $I(x, y, z)$ computed along the propagation direction z . The colormap shows intensity values normalized to the maximum.

Profile view comparisons of the simulated and experimental

Fig. 3. Simulation results of the diffracted field emerging from the beam homogenizer. (a) Is the 2D transect at $Y = 0$ of the intensity pattern through intensity profiles $I(x, y, z)$ computed at multiple observation planes (Z). (b) Profile view of the intensity distribution at selected Z . Blue lines are simulated intensities (smoothed to match photodiode dimensions), red dashed line are experimentally measured intensity profiles. (c) Experimental measurements of irradiance spatial distributions at selected propagation distances Z . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

intensities at selected three fixed propagation distances (z) are pictured in Fig. 3(b). Intensities are plotted along X at a fixed coordinate $Y = 0$, normalized to their respective peak values. Simulated profiles were smoothed with a moving average (uniform) filter with a 5 mm window in the object plane to reduce high-frequency noise. Experimental profiles were extracted at $Y = 0$ from the measured 2D spatial irradiance distributions shown in Fig. 3(c).

Fig. 3(c) shows 2D spatial irradiance distribution at same three z , measured by scanning a photodiode across the expanded and homogenized beam in x - y plane. Each map is a single frame of x - y irradiance distribution with pixel size of 5 mm \times 5 mm, corresponding to the active area of the photodiode.

Micro lens arrays exhibit similar to Talbot self-imaging properties of Fresnel diffraction field when illuminated by coherent laser sources, which leads to grating-like diffractive behavior of the emerging field pattern, with its irradiance distributed into periodic bright spots focused by the lenslets [23,27,28]. Finite distances at which reconstructed images of the original focal-plane intensity distribution of the MLA appear are conventionally called Fourier images (distances of which referred to as Talbot length). Works such as Winthrop and Worthington (1965) suggested intermediate intensity patterns located between object reconstructions, the so-called Fresnel images [28,29], at which the number of the foci of the lenslets are multiplied. Positions of self-images and multiplied foci from a microlens array are given by:

$$z_{\text{fresnel}} = (Q + N/M) \cdot \frac{2 \cdot p^2}{\lambda} \quad (3.1)$$

Where Q , N , M are integers with $N < M$.

Q is an integer number of full Talbot distance $\frac{2 \cdot p^2}{\lambda}$ (so-called Fourier images), corresponding to self-imaging periods of the array. At these positions, located at multiples of Q along the direction of propagation, the original focal-plane intensity distribution of the MLA is reconstructed.

N and M are small non-negative integers that define the fractional Talbot effect. When $N \neq 0$, their fraction N/M defines the Fresnel images positions. Fresnel images are copies of the original focal-plane intensity pattern of the array, but with increased frequency of light points. The number of foci per line (or column) is multiplied by a factor M (if odd) or $M/2$ (if M even).

Such behaviour is suggested in the simulated intensity profile (Fig. 3), formed by repeating patterns of varying numbers of foci that appear periodically over the propagation distance. The foci intensity patterns manifest as bright curved caustics. The dark bands observed in the Talbot carpet correspond to regions of reduced intensity as certain focal regions in Y lie outside the $Y = 0$ plane, resulting in diminished intensity at several regions in the 2D cross-section presented.

The simulation results indicate that the Gaussian envelope of the initial beam continues to shape the overall diffracted beam at the beginning of the propagation up to approximately the first Fourier image (at 263 mm for $Q = 1$). An example at a propagation distance $z = 100$ mm shows that the intensity profile maintains a strong Gaussian-like shape, although slightly flattened and wider. This model prediction is confirmed experimentally, where, at the same propagation distance of 100 mm, the overall spatial distribution of irradiance in the observation plane is a Gaussian-like beam.

With further propagation distances, the Gaussian envelope dissipates

Fig. 4. (a) Photograph of the homogenized beam projected onto a screen at its optimal plane (360 mm), showing an approximately $55 \times 55 \text{ mm}^2$ square profile. (b) Measured irradiance distribution of the beam. By excluding the edges, a $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ central segment achieves a high irradiance uniformity of 99.6 %. (c) Normalized irradiance distribution of the $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ segment. (d) Relative deviation (in %) of each measured point from the mean irradiance in the $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ segment.

progressively, and a flat-top profile starts to dominate the overall beam shape. Starting at around 350 mm the model suggests a remarkably homogeneous “flat-top” profile of the diffracted field of an area around $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$. With further distance (390 mm and beyond), gaussian-like traces subtly appear in the flat-top profile losing its uniformity. Experimental measurements show the flat top beam reaches a total area of around $55 \times 55 \text{ mm}^2$ (Fig. 4); by omitting the edges where the irradiance slowly drops off and selecting the plateau of intensity, the resulting $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ beam shows indeed to have an exceptional spatial uniformity of over 99.6 % at 360 mm, with beam inhomogeneity lower than 0.4 % (expressed as largest relative deviation of each measured point from the mean: $RD(\%) = \max_i \left(\left| \frac{E_i - \bar{E}}{\bar{E}} \right| \cdot 100 \right)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ where N is the number of sampled pixels). Taking 95 % of central pixels and further excluding border regions, the maximum relative non-uniformity drops below 0.3 %. As predicted by the model, further propagation distance shows subtle traces of Gaussian profile reconstructing. At these distances, the model has an approximately 15 % underestimation of propagated beam size.

Experimentally measured uniformity evolution of the beam with propagation distances around 340 mm and a 380 mm is shown in Fig. 5. According to these results, a uniformity above 99 % can be obtained with this setup at planes located between 350 mm and 370 mm, reaching maximum uniformity of 99.6 % at 360 mm.

3.1.1. Beamlets density and resolution

Interestingly, the high uniformity of the “flat-top” profile begins at around 350 mm, a distance matching a Fresnel image position of $N = 1$ and $M = 3$ (eq. (3.1)), suggesting at this distance, a tripling of foci numbers per coordinate. Furthermore, the homogeneous “flat-top” profile slowly starts to dissipate with traces of Gaussian profile recovering at 390 mm propagation distance, which, according to the definition at eq. (3.1), is equivalent to a Fresnel image with its original periodicity (that of the MLA) intact. Such behavior is indeed visible on the 2D intensity profile in Fig. 3(a) where simulated curved intensity caustics equivalent to beamlets are tripled at around 360 mm propagation distance versus at 390 mm where their number is equal to total number of illuminated lenslets. The spacing of beamlets scales with multiple factors such as the pitch p , fractional Talbot order (N/M) and

the effective beam size at the observation distance z .

Experimentally, the beamlet distribution in a $9 \times 9 \text{ mm}^2$ fragment of the expanded $55 \times 55 \text{ mm}^2$ “flat-top” beam at the working distance (360 mm), measured with a beam profiler (WinCamD-LCM), is presented on Fig. 6. The periodic MLA structure splits the input coherent laser beam into multiple beamlets separated by $630 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6 (c)), which is in good accordance with the unsmoothed model prediction, suggesting a separation distance of $610 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6 (d)). Dividing the side of the flat-top beam at 360 mm distance (around 57 mm total) by the distance between the beamlets yields 90 foci, approximately the triple of the 32 lenslets illuminated by the expanded Gaussian beam ($8 \text{ mm} / 250 \mu\text{m}$) in one coordinate.

Subsequently, the foci beamlets density reaches $3 / \text{mm}^2$ at the working distance. A typical 1 cm^2 diameter spectroradiometer optical entrance can thus contain around 235 such beamlets, sufficient for most detectors used in radiometry, such as optical power meters, spectroradiometers, or imaging sensors. As an example, a misalignment resulting in a 1 beamlet variation translates into a flux measurement variation of 0.43 %.

3.1.2. Repeatability of patterns at longer distances

Continuing the analysis of the self-imaging phenomenon and the periodicity of the optical field along the propagation axis, the irradiance distribution is expected to repeat at discrete planes separated by the Talbot length $z_T = \frac{2 \cdot p^2}{\lambda}$, which corresponds to an integer increment of Q in Eq. (3.1). For $Q = 2$, such plane is expected to be between 620 and 700 mm. Experimentally, a highly homogeneous irradiance distribution was observed at approximately 680 mm along the optical axis over a $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ segment of a $80 \times 80 \text{ mm}^2$ beam (measured with the $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ photodiode) (Fig. 7), effectively validating the Fresnel image recurrence.

At this observation plane, the measured separation between adjacent beamlets is approximately $1250 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 7(c)), resulting in 64 focal spots per coordinate axis. Thus, the homogeneous irradiance distribution at 680 mm corresponds to a Fresnel image with twice the number of initially illuminated 32 lenslets.

The Talbot effect and self-imaging phenomenon cease to persist after a certain distance, after which Fourier and Fresnel images vanish as diffraction orders cease to overlap. This upper limit, determined by the

Fig. 5. Beam uniformity evolution with propagation distance around the working distance. Blue squares are the mean of maximum relative irradiance deviations from the mean. Error bars are standard deviation of these relative deviation measurements. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Foci (beamlet) density is tripled at the Fresnel image located at 360 mm. (a) Photograph of the 55x55 mm² flat top beam at 360 mm². (b) Beam Profiler imaging of beamlets distribution of a 9x9 mm² segment of the beam. (c) Experimentally measured foci (beamlets) distance versus (d) simulated distances using the computational model.

Fig. 7. Recurrence of a Fresnel image and homogenized beam pattern at a plane situated around 680 mm. (a) Normalized irradiance distribution of the 50 × 50 mm² segment in an 80x80 mm² beam. (b) Relative deviation (in %) of each measured point from the mean irradiance in the 50 × 50 mm² segment. (c) Experimentally measured foci (beamlets) distance.

finite size of the grating (in this case, the microlens array), can be estimated by a Fresnel number requirement $N_f > 0.25 \frac{L}{p}$ or directly by the paraxial approximation [24]:

$$z_0 = \frac{L \cdot p}{\lambda} \quad (3.2)$$

Both methods yield, for a 475 nm wavelength in this setup, a distance of approximately 5 m beyond which the interference pattern required to form Talbot images disappears.

3.1.3. Wavelength Dependence of irradiance spatial distribution uniformity.

Similar simulations, measurements and analysis were conducted using a 632.8 nm (red) wavelength, emitted by a He-Ne laser. The model predicted uniform irradiance distributions at propagation distances located between 270 mm and 320 mm distances from the MLA. These predictions have been experimentally confirmed, yielding spatial uniformities exceeding 99.5 % at optimal planes around 300 mm. Although

this optimal plane lies closer to the MLA than in the 475 nm (blue) wavelength case, the increased diffractive spreading of the red light (Eq. (2.5)) compensates for the reduced propagation distance, producing a flat-top beam of roughly 40 × 40 mm², which is comparable in size to that obtained with the 475 nm laser.

The closer position of the optimal homogeneous plane to the MLA at 632.8 nm compared to the 475 nm case is due to the inverse scaling with wavelength of the Fourier and Fresnel Image positions (see Eq. (2.5)). Interestingly, for both wavelengths studied, the plane at which the irradiance profile achieves maximal uniformity lies approximately 100 mm beyond the first Fourier image ($Q = 1$ for Eq. (3.1)).

Achieving highly uniform spatial distributions at both extremities of the visible spectrum suggests that similarly high uniformities can be achieved at intermediate wavelengths within the VIS range. Thus, highly uniform Fresnel images in the spectral range from 475 nm to 630 nm are expected to lie between 300 mm and 360 mm from the MLA, and can probably be also extrapolated to a larger spectral region as well.

3.2. Temporal stability

Stable flux output is important in many applications to avoid temporal fluctuations in beam intensity, which can introduce significant errors, inconsistencies, and performance degradation. In this setup, a collimated 2 mm diameter Gaussian-shaped circular beam traverses the

LPC for temporal stabilization of the laser flux. A portion of the beam is sampled and continuously monitored by a remote detector, providing real-time feedback to the LPC. The stabilized laser beam exiting the LPC is directed to a detector, normally incident and underfilling detectors active surface, where its flux stability is measured (Fig. 8(a)). Fig. 8(a) illustrates the temporal stabilization performance over 48 h of

Fig. 8. Overall temporal stability of (a) 2 mm Gaussian collimated laser beam (48 h), and (b) Expanded laser beam overfilling the detector (16 h).

continuous operation, depicting the flux, the Relative Standard Deviation (RSTD) for each point, and the relative deviation (RD) of each point from the global mean of the dataset. Each data point represents the mean value of a 60-second measurement of the laser beam flux with a corresponding 60-second measurement of the dark current subtracted. The RSTD represents the relative standard deviation within each 60-second measurement period.

The RSTD remains consistently around 20 ppm throughout the 48-hour measurement duration, reflecting an exceptionally low variability for each point of the dataset. A single peak of 80 ppm occurs at the 23-hour mark, coinciding with a recalibration event of the LPC.

The RD is calculated as the relative difference of each point from the global mean, divided by the global mean. As shown in Fig. 8(a), during the initial hour of the measurement the LPC stabilization is inactive due to warming up and calibration. After this initial calibration phase, the LPC stabilization activates, reducing the laser flux to its target value. Following this recalibration phase, the Gaussian laser spot flux becomes exceptionally stable, with the RD remaining within 40 ppm until a second recalibration event. At the 23-hour mark, the LPC recalibrates, compensating for a slow drift in the laser flux and restoring it to the set value. Overall, beyond the initial calibration phase, the RD remains below 300 ppm for the whole 48 h. However, during the phases of highest stability, the RD of the laser flux is as low as 40 ppm for durations of at least 6 h, as illustrated in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8(b) illustrates the temporal stability performance of the expanded, flat-top homogenized beam overfilling the detector's active

surface over a 16-hour continuous operation. The beam undergoes expansion and homogenization following stabilization and its exit from the LPC, as described in Section 2.2.

The RSTD (Relative Standard Deviation) varies between 30 ppm and 80 ppm, with occasional peaks reaching 100 ppm during the 16-hour measurement period. This indicates low variability in the dataset but shows greater variability and a wider spread of values compared to the collimated Gaussian laser beam dataset. Similarly to the non-expanded 2 mm Gaussian beam, the expanded laser flux stabilizes after the initial LPC calibration phase, maintaining a consistent RD (Relative Deviation) within 0.05 % (500 ppm) over multiple hours of operation (Fig. 9). While the temporal stability of the expanded beam remains excellent, it is approximately an order of magnitude lower than the stability observed for the collimated Gaussian beam.

This decrease in temporal stability for the expanded beam, compared to the collimated Gaussian beam, may be attributed to the overfilling of the detector's active surface by the expanded beam. As described in Subsection 3.1.1. and illustrated in Fig. 6, the expanded, homogenized beam is a dense composition of small Gaussian-shaped beamlets produced by the fractional Talbot effect [30]. A possible reason for these observed temporal variations in flux measurements of the expanded beam are minor vibrations or slight positional drifts over time of the beamlets incident at the edges of the detector's active surface.

Fig. 9. Temporal stability in highly stable phases (7 h) of the 2 mm Gaussian collimated laser beam and Expanded laser beam overfilling the detector.

3.3. Optical flux and uncertainty budget

The optical flux output is summarized in Table 2:

Output flux of 2 mW generates an irradiance of 870 mWm^{-2} of the expanded beam at distance 350 mm from the MLA. Outdoor spectral solar irradiance around 475 nm is at most $2 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{nm}^{-1}$ [31], which is in the same order as the irradiance of the final output beam. The optical flux is thus suitable for detectors typically used in solar applications.

For applications requiring higher powers, a substitution of the laser with a source of higher flux output is possible up to 4 W, the LPC being the upper limit on the source flux. Additionally, AR coating of components in the beam homogenizer, and a substitution of the beam splitter by an 1:99 (R:T) alternative could reduce optical losses and improve the power yield of the setup, potentially reaching 0.8 W flux and an irradiance of 350 Wm^{-2} .

We estimate the main factors of uncertainty of irradiance to be the spatial homogeneity of the beam (rectangular distribution) and temporal fluctuations (Gaussian distributed). The uncertainty budget of an irradiance measurement of the homogenized beam within its $45 \times 45 \text{ mm}^2$ segment is summarized in Table 3.

Thus, the irradiance value generated by the setup falls within an expanded relative uncertainty of 0.46 %. This uncertainty is below previously reported highly reliable irradiance systems with uncertainties of about 1 % [16,21], and is comparable to state-of-the-art integrating sphere-based sources that reach values as low as 0.2 % [15,19,20]. Comparing to such sphere-based systems, this approach is relatively compact and simple employing commercial components, and produces a well-directed, large-area uniform flat-top beam with tuneable sizes. The system offers adaptability to different detector apertures and wavelengths in the VIS region, is stabilized non-invasively on the laser, while maintaining higher irradiance levels due to its low optical losses and avoiding fluorescence at any wavelength.

Paired with extremely reliable detectors, such as the Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector (PQED)[32,32,33], the system can provide extremely reliable readings of irradiance or flux in the visible and NIR range.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates an approach to design a simple setup for generating highly reliable and stable monochromatic irradiance distributions in the visible and NIR ranges. By leveraging the self-imaging properties of periodic MLA structures, effectiveness of commercially available microlens arrays (MLAs) in expanding and achieving lossless beam homogenization reaching 99.6 % uniformity has been demonstrated. The spatial behaviour and properties of the output beam can be computationally modelled using near-field diffraction analyses and the fractional Talbot effect. These results suggest a platform for obtaining extremely stable and reliable irradiance values potentially of interest to a variety of applications such as radiometry, laser processing, optical metrology, imaging and device characterization systems. Limits to potential applications can arise due to specific irradiance requirements (above several hundreds of Wm^{-2}) and resolution constraints of used detection systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Salim Ferhat: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Julian Gröbner:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Table 2

Output optical flux evaluation of the expanded homogenized beam. †Manufacturer data, *measured.

Parameter	Contribution	Flux (mW)
475 nm Laser source	+100 %	10
Half-wave plate	-0.25 % †	
LPC	-10 % *	
Spatial Filter	-30 % *	
Beamsplitter	-20 % *	
Beam homogenizer	-18 % *	
Mirrors (combined)	-2% †	
Output flux		2
Output irradiance at working distance ($z = 360 \text{ mm}$)		
870 (mWm^{-2})		

Table 3

Uncertainty budget of irradiance measurement generated by the setup.

Factor	Relative Standard Uncertainty (overfilled detector)
Temporal variation	0.027 %
Spatial distribution	0.23 %
Relative uncertainty Combined	0.23 %
Relative expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.46 %

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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